

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Vocational School English Analysis Class (IKN- Science Sains)

Object ;

Aprida Anggraini paper analysis for *Representation Of The King's Rhetorical Power In The King'sking's Speech*

Background and Analysis

This writing aims to portray King George VI (Bertie) in the film *The King Speech*. The history of this writing tells how a king is not fluent in speaking. The icon used to deconstruct the meaning contained in this film reflects the icon of the king in the film "The King Speech", such as the level of actuality, representation, and ideology. This methodology is used to obtain data comprehensive so that the researcher conducts qualitative data analysis interactively and continuously with the following stages: reduction, presentation, verification, and conclusion. This film represents a king who is different from other rulers. This king has a stuttering problem but he has the advantage of speaking in front of his subjects. This writing describes the efforts of a king who stuttered to speak eloquently and loudly in front of his people, but he realized he had many shortcomings he could not escape from his position as king. Since the country's situation is unpredictable, it must be able to convey a message that he wanted to convey through a state speech. In the end, he received a speech that was quite satisfying, able to build enthusiasm in the community and build the spirit to be calm and united in the face of a disaster.

The article, as can be seen, summarizes the results of the analysis without making any claims to completeness. The findings support the theory that King George VI's and Queen Elizabeth II's prayers are part of the history of rhetoric in the twentieth and twenty-first centuries and contribute to the legacy of present royal rhetoric. It was also determined that speeches were delivered using modern media for the period in question: radio in 1939 and the Internet in 2020; taking into account the affordability of communication channels to reach a large audience.

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Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions :

1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,

.Yes, there is data that is carried out in this journal by analyzing and obtaining information

2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

Yes, the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as In some parts of research papers, the content comes from secondary sources from online websites, and journals, the qualitative part of the research is carried out by observing several factors to find out the hidden meaning of the film itself based on the results of qualitative research.

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

Yes, This Journal Identified through previous research, this paper meets the requirements of originality because it is my own idea and thought.

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

This paper does not make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science.

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

The issues that occur do not contain conflicts because the lessons taken or researched are moral messages that can be practiced

6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and

The formulation of the problem is found in every research that is expected for the reader community to understand the journal we are discussing

7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

The purpose of this research is to add insight into anything

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

Once upon a time, when Britain was at war with Hitler/Germany, Prince Albert had to give a welcoming speech, this was one of the first major speeches after serving as king. At that moment Prince Albert was very scared and asked Logue to help him with this speech. At that time his wife and Logue also gave mental support to Prince Albert so that he could make this

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speech well. When the speech arrived, Prince Albert was accompanied by Logue in his speech so that Prince Albert could speak smoothly and well.

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

In this film, many examples are worthy of emulation. Increasing self-confidence is very important, especially when public speaking. Confidence is like a building foundation. If our self-confidence is weak, then the efforts we have made can easily collapse. When we maintain our image in the eyes of others we must be able to communicate assertively and everything we do must be with confidence. To build our confidence, we must identify what the problem is within ourselves. Once we know what the problem is with us, then we must try to break the vicious cycle of our self-doubt.

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